

Syntheses of 6-Hydroxyluteolin and Sinensetin by Wessely – Moser Rearrangement

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Syntheses of 6-hydroxyluteolin (1) and sinensetin (2) are described. The compounds 6 and 7 afford 1 on Wessely – Moser rearrangement. The synthetic samples 1 and 2 are identical (m.m.p. and co-ir) with the authentic samples.

HARBORNE^{1,2} reported the isolation of 6-hydroxyluteolin, a new pigment, from the fresh leaves of *Catalpa bignonioides*, *C. speciosa* and in herbarium material of *C. bungei* and *Tecoma australis*. This pigment was isolated as the 7-glucoside along with luteolin-7-glucoside. On hydrolysis, the glucoside gave glucose and a flavone formulated as 5,6,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone (1) rested on the degradation and spectral characteristics. The methylated product of 1 was identical with the natural sample sinensetin (2) isolated from *Citrus sinensis*³, *C. aurantium*⁴, *Eupatorium coelestinum*⁵ and the structure of 2 was finally confirmed by the methylation of eupatilin (3) obtained from *Eupatorium semiseratum* DC⁶. The flavone (1) had earlier been secured by the demethylation of the authentic natural product sinensetin with pyridine hydrobromide⁷. The present paper deals with the synthesis of 6-hydroxyluteolin and sinensetin by Wessely – Moser rearrangement thereby confirming their proposed structures 1 and 2, respectively.

- 1, R=R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=H (6-Hydroxyluteolin)
2, R=R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=CH₃ (Sinensetin)
3, R=R¹=R⁴=CH₃, R²=R³=H (Eupatilin)
4, R=R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=COOH,

- 5, R=R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=CH₃,
6, R=R¹=R²=R³=R⁴=CH₃, R⁵=H
7, R=R¹=R⁴=CH₃, R²=R³=H
8, R=R¹=R⁴=CH₃, R²=R³=CH₂C₆H₅

- 9, R¹=R²=H
10, R¹=H, R²=CO.C₆H₄(OCH₃)₂(3:4)
11, R¹=CO.C₆H₄(OCH₃)₂(3:4), R²=H

To embark upon the synthesis of 1 and 2, 5-hydroxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (6) or 5,7-dihydroxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (7) was selected as the key intermediate and the ring isomerisation by Wessely – Moser rearrangement has been successfully applied. Compound 6 had earlier been synthesised by (i) Allan – Robinson condensation⁸⁻¹⁰ of 2,4-dihydroxy-3,6-dimethoxyacetophenone and veratric anhydride, (ii) Baker – Venkataraman rearrangement¹¹⁻¹³ of 2-veratroxyloxy-3,4-dimethoxy-6-benzyloxyacetophenone, (iii) through chalcone formation¹⁴ and (iv) by Baker – Venkataraman rearrangement of 2-veratroxyloxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone followed by demethylation, persulphate oxidation and methylation with diazomethane¹⁵. These methods involve a number of cumbersome steps with a very poor yield. The alternative procedure which we have adopted in the present synthesis is unambiguous and convenient.

2-Hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (9) secured by the Friedel – Crafts' acylation of 1,2,3,5-tetramethoxybenzene¹⁶, on condensation with 3,4-dimethoxybenzoyl chloride afforded 2-(3',4'-dimethoxybenzyloxy)-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (10). This ester, when treated with KOH in pyridine underwent Baker – Venkataraman rearrangement to give 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-3',4'-dimethoxydibenzoylmethane (11) which on cyclodehydration with acetic acid and sodium acetate furnished 5,7,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone (5). Compound 5 underwent demethylation on refluxing with anhydrous aluminium chloride in acetonitrile to yield

5-hydroxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (6). It showed ir absorption at 1658 cm^{-1} for a carbonyl group. The pmr spectra of the compound showed besides other signals, a broad band integrated for a proton at δ 12.6 in downfield region which was exchangeable with deuterium. It was undoubtedly due to OH group in the compound. Such a downfield resonance of hydroxyl proton clearly indicates to be *peri* to the carbonyl group (see Experimental).

5,7-Dibenzoyloxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (8) on catalytic dehydrogenation gave 5,7-dihydroxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (7)¹². Both the compounds 6 and 7 on ring-isomerisation with hydriodic acid afforded the same product identified as 5,6,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone (1) on spectral studies and was identical with the natural sample of 6-hydroxyluteolin.

The flavone (1) on subsequent methylation with $(\text{Me})_2\text{SO}_4 - \text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$ in acetone yielded 5,6,7,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone (2) which was also identical with the authentic sample of sinensetin.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 and 577 spectrophotometers. The pmr spectra were recorded in different laboratories using TMS as an internal standard.

2-(3',4'-Dimethoxybenzyloxy)-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (10): 3,4-Dimethoxybenzoyl chloride prepared from 3,4-dimethoxybenzoic acid (1.3 g) was heated at 100° with a solution of 2-hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxyacetophenone (9; 1.0 g) in dry pyridine (5 ml) for 1 h. The reaction mixture was poured into water. Sufficient HCl was then added to remove pyridine. The solid mass thus separated was filtered, washed with 10% sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. The ester was crystallised from acetone-alcohol as colourless long needles, m.p. $197-98^\circ$ (Found: C, 61.15; H, 6.01. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 61.53; H, 5.68%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O) and 1675 cm^{-1} (COCH_3).

2-Hydroxy-3,4,6-trimethoxy-3',4'-dimethoxydibenzoylmethane (11): The above ester (1.0 g) was dissolved in pyridine (10 ml) and stirred at 60° after the addition of powdered KOH (1.5 g) for 3 h. The yellow solid separated out was filtered, washed and crystallised from benzene as yellow needles, m.p. $172-73^\circ$ (Found: C, 61.35; H, 6.41. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$ requires: C, 61.53; H, 5.68%). It gave positive ferric chloride test and was soluble in 10% alkali solution.

5,7,8,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone (5): A mixture of the diketone (11; 1.0 g), fused sodium acetate (1.5 g) and glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 h. Acetic acid was then removed under reduced pressure and the residual liquid poured into crushed ice. The solid that separated out was filtered, washed and crystallised from ethyl

acetate as white needles, m.p. $197-98^\circ$ (Found: C, 64.43; H, 5.62. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 64.51; H, 5.41%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1640 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 4.20 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.0 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.99-3.98 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 3.96 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.64 (1H, s, H-3), 6.47 (1H, s, H-6), 7.47 (d, H-2'), 7.03 (d, H-5') and 7.59 (d, H-6').

5-Hydroxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (6): 5,7,8,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone (5; 0.5 g) was dissolved in dry acetonitrile (30 ml) and the solution refluxed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.0 g) for 2 h on a water-bath. The solvent was then removed and the complex was decomposed by heating with cold and dilute HCl (1:1, 15 ml) for 15 min and the product filtered. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. $210-11^\circ$ (Found: C, 63.49; H, 5.21. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 63.68; H, 5.06%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1635 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 3.98 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 4.00 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCH}_3$), 6.46 (1H, s, H-6), 6.62 (1H, s, H-3), 7.03 (d, H-5'), 7.50 (d, H-2'), 7.55 (d, H-6') and 12.6 (bs-OH).

5,7-Dihydroxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (7): A mixture of 5,7-dibenzoyloxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (8; 0.3 g) and palladised charcoal (10%, 90 mg) in a mixed solvent of ethyl acetate and methanol was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen for 4 h. It was filtered and the solvent was removed. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethyl acetate to yield 5,7-dihydroxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (150 mg) as yellow prisms, m.p. $217-18^\circ$ (lit.¹² $217-18^\circ$) (Found: C, 62.58; H, 5.03. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 62.79; H, 4.68%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1635 cm^{-1} (C=O).

5,6,7,3',4'-Pentahydroxyflavone (6-hydroxyluteoline) (1): A mixture of 5-hydroxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (6; 1.0 g), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and hydriodic acid (*d* 1.5; 5 ml) was heated under reflux at $140-50^\circ$ (oil-bath) for 2 h and the cooled mixture poured into a saturated solution of sodium hydrogen sulphite. The precipitate was boiled with water and filtered, and was crystallised from amyl alcohol as yellow crystals, m.p. $326-27^\circ$ (lit.⁷ 325°) (Found: C, 59.46; H, 3.96. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$ requires: C, 59.61; H, 3.34%).

The same experiment was repeated with 5,7-dihydroxy-8,3',4'-trimethoxyflavone (7) and the same product was obtained. The products obtained by both the compounds 6 and 7 were identical in all respects (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir) with the authentic sample.

5,6,7,3',4'-Pentamethoxyflavone (sinensetin) (2): 5,6,7,3',4'-Pentahydroxyflavone (0.1 g) was refluxed with dimethylsulphate (1 ml), dry potassium carbonate (3.0 g) and dry acetone (20 ml) for 20 h. On the usual workup the resulting green oil was chromatographed on neutral alumina using chloroform as the eluent. On evaporation, the eluent afforded light yellow crystals of 5,6,7,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone (2; 70 mg), m.p. $175-76^\circ$ (lit.⁶ $175-76^\circ$) identical with the authentic sample.

5,6,7,3',4'-Pentaacetoxyflavone (4) was secured by slightly heating a mixture of 5,6,7,3',4'-pentahydroxyflavone (1 : 0.5 g), acetic anhydride and pyridine catalyst, as white needles, m.p. 243-44 (lit.[†] 241-43°).

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